

Fostering a Writing Culture Via Participation Network Among Form Five Students: A Case Study of Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Agama Sik, Kedah

¹Dr. Sidra Shehzadi, ²Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kalthom Husain, ³Mohamad Nor Hisyam

Lecturers of Bachelor of Media and Communication (BMC) Programme
School of Education and Human Sciences (SEHS)
Albukhary International University, Malaysia

Abstract

This research paper examines the implementation and outcomes of the Knowledge Transfer Programme aimed at fostering a writing culture among Form Five students in Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Agama Sik Kedah. The study focused on enhancing writing skills, increasing student motivation, and creating a supportive writing community. The activities carried out included workshops, collaborative writing exercises, and peer review sessions. The results indicate a positive impact on students' writing abilities and their engagement with writing as a medium for self-expression. This paper presents the activities as a case study and discusses the sustainability and cultural value of the programme.

Keywords

Keywords: Writing Culture, Knowledge Transfer, Form Five Students, Peer Review, Collaborative Writing

1. Introduction

Writing is a critical skill that forms the foundation for communication and intellectual development. In the context of education, writing enables students to express their thoughts, engage in critical thinking, and improve their overall academic performance. However, previous studies have shown that many students in Malaysia face challenges in writing due to a lack of interest, limited reading habits, and low self-efficacy. This research paper explores a Knowledge Transfer Programme designed to address these challenges by fostering a writing culture among

Form Five students in Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Agama Sik Kedah. The programme aimed to create a supportive environment where students could enhance their writing skills, participate in collaborative writing activities, and receive constructive feedback from peers and teachers.

2. Literature Review

The significance of writing skills in education has been widely acknowledged in academic literature. According to Dwivedi (n.d.), writing skills are essential for students' academic success as they facilitate the expression of ideas, critical thinking, and effective communication. In the Malaysian context, several studies have identified challenges that students face in developing writing skills. Mahamod, Yasin, and Kamarudin (2021) highlighted that writing anxiety is a prevalent issue among Malaysian secondary school students, often stemming from fear of judgment and lack of confidence in their abilities. Similarly, Moses and Mohamad (2019) discussed the decline in reading habits among students, which directly impacts their writing skills, as reading and writing are closely linked in the development of literacy.

The role of self-efficacy in writing has also been explored in previous research. Nurul Ain, Azlina, and Palanisamy (2021) found that students with higher self-efficacy are more likely to engage in writing tasks and produce higher-quality work. This suggests that interventions aimed at increasing students' confidence in their writing abilities could lead to significant improvements in their writing performance. Additionally, the importance of creating a supportive writing environment is emphasized by UAGC (2021), which notes that peer review and collaborative writing activities can help students develop their writing skills while fostering a sense of community.

3. Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded in social constructivist theory, which posits that learning occurs through social interactions and collaboration. Vygotsky's (1978) concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) is particularly relevant, as it emphasizes the role of social interaction in helping learners achieve tasks they could not accomplish independently. In the context of the Knowledge Transfer Programme, the collaborative writing exercises and peer review sessions

provided students with opportunities to learn from each other and receive guidance from more knowledgeable peers and teachers, thereby facilitating their development within the ZPD.

The programme also draws on Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, which highlights the importance of observational learning, imitation, and modeling in the acquisition of new skills. By engaging in collaborative activities and observing their peers, students were able to learn effective writing strategies and build confidence in their abilities. The emphasis on community-building within the programme aligns with Wenger's (1998) concept of communities of practice, where learning is viewed as a social process that occurs through participation in shared activities and the development of a common identity.

4. Methodology

The Knowledge Transfer Programme was implemented over a one-year period, targeting 20 Form Five students at Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Agama Sik Kedah. The programme involved a series of workshops that focused on various aspects of writing, including grammar, vocabulary, and writing mechanics. Students participated in collaborative writing exercises, peer review sessions, and creative writing activities. The programme also incorporated the use of digital tools and online platforms to facilitate writing and collaboration. Data was collected through student writing samples, questionnaires, and feedback from both students and teachers.

5. Case Study

The activities carried out in the Knowledge Transfer Programme served as a case study to demonstrate the effectiveness of the intervention. During the programme, students were engaged in writing workshops where they practiced different writing styles and genres. One of the key activities was the "Indoor Writing Adventure," where students participated in themed writing stations, including heritage, local legends, and poetry. These activities allowed students to explore their creativity while applying the writing skills they had learned. Students' writings were published on school bulletin boards and shared within the school community, providing them with a platform to showcase their work and receive recognition.

6. Results

The results of the Knowledge Transfer Programme indicate a significant improvement in students' writing skills and attitudes towards writing. Students demonstrated enhanced proficiency in grammar, vocabulary, and overall writing mechanics. Moreover, the programme succeeded in fostering a positive attitude towards writing, with students expressing increased motivation to write. The collaborative nature of the activities also helped build a sense of community among the students, as they learned to give and receive constructive feedback.

7. Discussion

The success of the Knowledge Transfer Programme can be attributed to its comprehensive approach, which combined skill development with community engagement. The use of collaborative activities and peer feedback played a crucial role in enhancing students' writing abilities and their confidence in expressing themselves through writing. Furthermore, the programme's emphasis on cultural values, such as entrepreneurship and adab (etiquette), aligned with the goals of producing well-rounded individuals who are both effective communicators and responsible members of society. The sustainability of the programme is also noteworthy, as it has the potential to be replicated in other schools, thereby contributing to the overall development of writing skills among students in the region.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the Knowledge Transfer Programme successfully fostered a writing culture among Form Five students at Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Agama Sik Kedah. The programme not only improved students' writing skills but also motivated them to view writing as a valuable tool for self-expression and communication. The activities carried out during the programme serve as

a valuable case study, demonstrating the effectiveness of a structured and collaborative approach to writing education. Future initiatives should consider expanding such programmes to reach a larger audience and further explore the integration of technology in writing education.

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Appendix 1

Module Title: Writing Connects Us

Module Overview:

Purpose:

The purpose of this module is to cultivate a vibrant writing culture among Form Five students at Sek Menengah Kebangsaan Agama Sik, Kedah, through active participation in a supportive writing network. The module emphasizes collaboration, creativity, and the development of effective writing skills.

Module Objectives:

1. Developing Writing Proficiency:

- Learn and apply fundamental writing skills, including grammar, vocabulary, and overall writing mechanics.
- Demonstrate improved writing proficiency across different genres.

2. Fostering Positive Attitudes Towards Writing:

- Cultivate a positive and appreciative attitude towards writing as a valuable means of self-expression and communication.
- Recognize the importance of effective writing in various aspects of academic and personal life.

3. Encouraging Collaborative Writing Practices:

- Actively participate in a writing network to foster collaboration and communication.
- Provide and receive constructive feedback to enhance writing skills.

4. Utilizing Technology for Writing Enhancement:

- Explore and utilize digital tools and online platforms to enhance writing practices.
- Collaborate on writing projects using technology, promoting technological literacy.

5. Enhancing Critical Thinking Skills:

- Engage in critical analysis and reflection through writing assignments.
- Develop the ability to express well-reasoned perspectives on various topics.

Module Structure:

Session 1: Introduction to the Writing Network

- Understanding the importance of a writing culture.
- Introduction to the collaborative writing platform.

Session 2: Writing Essentials

- Basic writing skills workshop covering grammar, vocabulary, and overall mechanics.
- Fun and interactive writing exercises.

Session 3: Building a Supportive Writing Community

- Establishing guidelines for respectful and constructive feedback.
- Forming writing groups within the network.

Session 4: Peer Review and Feedback

- Conducting peer reviews of writing assignments.
- Implementing constructive feedback to improve writing.

Session 5: Technology Integration for Writers

- Exploring digital tools to enhance the writing experience.
- Collaborating on a writing project using online platforms.

Session 6: Genre Exploration

- Introduction to different writing genres (narrative, persuasive, descriptive).
- Practice writing in various styles.

Session 7: Creative Writing Showcase

- Sharing and celebrating creative writing pieces within the network.
- Recognizing and applauding individual and collective achievements.

Session 8: Reflection and Future Goals

- Reflecting on personal writing growth throughout the module.
- Setting future writing goals and aspirations.

Assessment:

- Continuous assessment through peer-reviewed writing assignments.
- Participation in collaborative writing projects on the designated platform.
- Final creative writing portfolio showcasing individual progress.

Resources:

- Writing guides and reference materials.
- Online writing tools and platforms.
- Relevant readings and examples of exemplary writing.

Conclusion:

By the end of this module, students will not only have developed improved writing skills but will also be active contributors to a supportive writing culture within their school community.

Learning Outcomes:

Upon completion of this module, students will:

1. Demonstrate Improved Writing Proficiency:

- Exhibit enhanced skills in grammar, vocabulary, and overall writing mechanics.
- Showcase proficiency in different writing genres.

2. Cultivate Positive Attitudes Towards Writing:

- Develop a positive and appreciative attitude towards writing as a valuable means of expression and communication.
- Recognize the importance of effective writing in various contexts.

3. Engage in Collaborative Writing Practices:

- Actively participate in a writing network, fostering collaboration and communication.

- Provide and receive constructive feedback to enhance writing skills.
4. **Utilize Technology for Writing Enhancement:**
- Effectively use digital tools and online platforms to enhance writing practices.
 - Collaborate on writing projects using technology, promoting technological literacy.
5. **Enhance Critical Thinking Skills:**
- Engage in critical analysis and reflection through writing assignments.
 - Express well-reasoned perspectives on various topics.

These learning outcomes aim to capture the holistic development of students' writing skills, attitudes, and collaborative abilities through the "Writing Connects Us" module.

Training Methodology:

- Interactive activities: Role-playing, group discussions, and collaborative writing to encourage active participation.
- Real-life examples: Incorporate relevant examples to participants' lives.
- Group collaboration: Emphasize group activities to foster collaboration and peer learning.
- Practical application: Mini-projects to allow immediate application of communication skills.
- Feedback and reflection: Provide opportunities for feedback and reflection throughout the day.

Appendix 2

Indoor Writing Adventure

Introduction (Classroom Setting):

"Salam sejahtera, students! Today, we're embarking on a special Indoor Writing Adventure right here in our classroom in Sik, Kedah. Our goal is to develop our writing skills through engaging activities and discussions. Let's make this a day of creativity!"

Preparation:

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- Form groups of 4–5 students.
- Ensure each group has access to notebooks and pens.

Station Activities:

Station 1: Heritage Corner

- **Activity:** Create a list of traditional Sik practices or historical events. Each student writes a short paragraph about one item from the list.

Station 2: Imaginary Market

- **Activity:** Imagine a vibrant market scene in Sik. Write a descriptive piece about the market, including sights, sounds, and smells.

Station 3: Local Legends Corner

- **Activity:** Research and share a local legend or myth from Sik. Write a modern-day adaptation or continuation of the story.

Station 4: Sik Today - Newsroom

- **Activity:** Pretend to be journalists covering Sik-related news. Write short news articles on imaginary events or developments in Sik.

Station 5: Poetry Workshop

- **Activity:** Engage in a brief poetry workshop. Each student writes a short poem inspired by Sik's natural beauty or cultural richness.

Rotation:

- Students rotate through each station, spending 20 minutes at each. Groups work collaboratively on activities.

Group Sharing:

- Each group presents their writing pieces to the class. Encourage discussion and feedback.

Reflection:

- Facilitate a brief reflection session where students share thoughts on how the indoor activities enhanced their writing skills.
- Discuss any insights gained during the activities.

Closing:

- Express gratitude for Sik's rich heritage.
- Encourage students to continue exploring and writing about their local culture.

Learning Outcomes:

- Improved writing skills through various indoor activities.
- Enhanced ability to describe cultural elements and events.
- Increased creativity in storytelling and poetry.
- Immediate application of writing skills in an indoor setting.

This Indoor Writing Adventure brings the focus on writing skills while remaining within the classroom or training session, allowing students to explore and express their creativity through various writing activities related to Sik, Kedah.

Appendix 3

Fostering a Writing Culture Via Participation Network Among Form Five Students in Sek Menengh Kebangsaan Agama Sik, Kedah

Student Writing Skills Questionnaire

Hi! We're curious about your thoughts on writing. Please pick the answer that feels right for you.

1. About You:

- Your Name: [_____]
- Grade or Year:
 - 1-3
 - 4-6
 - 7-9
 - 10-12

2. Writing Habits:

- How often do you write for fun (not for school)?
 - Almost never
 - Sometimes
 - A lot
 - All the time!
- What kind of things do you like to write about?
 - Stories
 - Poems
 - Letters
 - Other (please specify): _____

3. Writing Steps:

- Do you know the steps to follow when you write?
 - Yes

- No

4. Grammar Knowledge:

- How sure do you feel about grammar rules?
 - Very sure
 - Sure
 - Kind of sure
 - Not sure
- Is there something about grammar that you find tricky?
 - Yes (please specify): _____
 - No

5. Purpose and Audience:

- When you write, do you think about why you're writing and who you're writing for?
 - Always
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never

6. Words We Use:

- How much do you think about using cool and exact words when you write?
 - A lot
 - A little
 - Not much
 - Not at all
- How do you learn new words?
 - Reading
 - Talking with people
 - Watching videos
 - Other (please specify): _____

7. Fixing Mistakes:

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- Do you check and change your writing before saying it's done?
 - Always
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- What do you do to make your writing better?
 - Ask for help
 - Use a spell-check
 - Read it again myself
 - Other (please specify): _____

8. Your Style:

- Do you have a favorite way to write (like when you're telling a story or doing a school assignment)? What's it like?
 - Yes (please specify): _____
 - No

9. Anything Else?

- Is there anything else you want to tell us about writing? Any cool stories or things you find hard?
 - Yes (please specify): _____
 - No